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Framing the Calamity: The Coal Crisis within Public Debate in Prague and Beyond, 1914–1918

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Abstract

This article examines the socio-discursive construction of coal scarcity in Prague during World War I, and analyses how scarcity resonated in the public debate. It combines the use of content analysis and operationalisation of the framing theory to investigate how the Czech-written period press framed the coal scarcity during the WWI, and how the Czech-written media, censorship notwithstanding, suggested that coal scarcity be remembered. The main findings suggest that despite the use of crisis terminology and emotional-driven language (calamity), coal scarcity remained a marginal and contained issue in public discourse during the early stages of war, while later, from 1916 onwards, the framing shifted, and the reassuring tone used earlier evolved into an openly critical discourse. It furthermore underscores that coal-dependency rendered the urban communities more vulnerable not only to material shortages but also to discursive manipulation.

Key words: coal crisis, Habsburg Monarchy, media discourse, World War I, framing

War always causes suffering, material deprivation, and disruption to all warring countries. Disruption of supply chains and existing infrastructures, along with conscription and a shortage of skilled labour and materials, has a profound impact on the situation in individual countries. In the case of the World War I, rationing became a daily reality and shortages were evident in almost every aspect of life.¹ While much has been written on the accounts of World War I in individual nation states, large body of scholarly literature has also explored the issues of daily life both at the front and in the rear, including the problems related to supply.²

¹ Steven BELLER, *The Habsburg Monarchy, 1815–1918*, Cambridge 2018, p. 268; Max Stephan SCHULTZE, *Austria-Hungary's Economy in World War I*. In: Stephen BROADBERRY–Mark HARRISON (Eds.), *The Economics of World War I*, Cambridge 2005, pp. 77–111.

² Rudolf KUČERA, *Rationed Life: Science, Everyday Life, and Working-Class Politics in the Bohemian Lands, 1914–1918*, Berghahn Books 2019; Thierry BONZON –Belinda J. DAVIS, *Feeding the Cities*. In: Jay WINTER – Jean-Louis ROBERT, *Capital Cities at War: Paris, London, Berlin 1914–1919*, Cambridge 1999, pp. 305–341; Jenny SPRENGER-SEYFFARTH, *Kriegsküchen in Wien und Berlin: Öffentliche Massenverpflegung und private Familienmahlzeit im und nach dem Ersten Weltkrieg*, Bielefeld 2023; Maureen HEALY, *Introductory Remarks: Space, Chronology and the Habsburg Home Fronts*, *European Review of History: Revue Européenne d'histoire* 24, 2017, no. 2, p. 176; Belinda J. DAVIS, *Home Fires Burning. Food, Politics, and Everyday Life in World War*

Concerning the latter, studies focusing on capital cities and metropolitan areas have proliferated (cf. London, Paris, Berlin, Vienna, Warsaw, and most recently also Prague).³ The Bohemian Lands, the largest province of Cisleithanian Austria, have likewise been studied with respect to wartime shortages, rationing, and daily life.⁴ Not all the aspects of wartime scarcity have, however, received attention. The topic of energy history or wartime energy scarcity in general remains one of those areas that are relatively less explored despite the fact that partial pivot accounts already exist.⁵

As scarcity is mostly caused by energy supply problems, the latter occurred in most warring countries, and scarcity equally impacted the Habsburg Monarchy, most notably its most industrialized part, the Cisleithania. Energy scarcity evolved mostly around coal, the then critically important energy source for both households and industry. From 1880 through 1914, coal surpassed wood and became the main source of energy within the Monarchy.⁶ By 1910, coal constituted already 33 percent of the Monarchy's total primary energy use.⁷ In 1913, the Monarchy consumed nearly 60 million tons⁸ of fossil fuels (hard coal, lignite, and coke), while the Cisleithanian Austria was able to cover nearly 90 percent of its needs. As a result, it had to import 10 and during certain periods even 20 percent of its overall consumption.⁹ In contrast, Hungary consumed between one quarter and one fifth of the Empire's coal while it was able to cover only 60 percent of its needs. In 1913, Hungary could satisfy only 23 percent of its overall

I Berlin, Chapel Hill 2000; Maureen HEALY, *Vienna and the Fall of the Habsburg Empire: Total War and Everyday Life in World War I*, Cambridge 2004; WINTER – ROBERT (Eds.), *Capital Cities at War: Paris, London, Berlin 1914–1919*, Cambridge 1999.

³ Claire MORELON, *Streetscapes of War and Revolution, Prague, 1914–1920*, Cambridge 2024; Olga FEJTOVÁ et al. (Eds.), *Nezměrné ztráty a jejich zvládní. Obyvatelstvo evropských velkoměst a I. světová válka* [Immeasurable Losses and Coping with Them. The Population of European Cities and World War I], Prague 2016.

⁴ Jiří HUTEČKA, *Wartime Provisioning, the People, and the State in Habsburg Central Europe during World War I*, *Střed/Centre*, 2024, no. 1, pp. 80–97, <https://doi.org/10.54681/c.2024.1.4>; Jiří HUTEČKA, *Politics of Urban Space in the Wartime Habsburg Monarchy: Olmütz/Olomouc, 1914 to 1919*, *Austrian History Yearbook*, 2025, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0067237825100349>.

⁵ Thierry BONZON, *Coal and the Metropolis*. In: WINTER – ROBERT, *Capital Cities at War*, pp. 342–73; Pierre CHANCEREL, L'approvisionnement en charbon de l'industrie française pendant la Première Guerre Mondiale. In: P. FRIEDENSON – P. GRISET (Eds.), *L'Industrie dans la Grande Guerre*, pp. 135–149; Pierre CHANCEREL, *Coal Logistics: a key issue in economic mobilization*, *Guerres mondiales et conflits contemporains* 266, 2017, no. 2, pp. 23–36; Aliaksandr PIAHANAU, 'Each Wagon of Coal Should be Paid for with Territorial concessions' Hungary, Czechoslovakia, and the Coal Shortage in 1918–21, *Diplomacy and Statecraft* 34, 2023, no. 1, pp. 86–116; N. BOGOMAZOV, *The Outbreak of World War I and Coal Shortages in Warsaw: How Railways saved the City in September 1914*, *Journal of Energy History/ Revue d'histoire de l'énergie* 14, 2025, (in print) no. 1; Marcela HENNLICHOVÁ, *Narratives of Crisis*, *Journal of Energy History/ Revue d'histoire de l'énergie* 14, 2025, no. 1, 64–79.

⁶ Ségolène PLYER, *Fuelling the Diversity: A Regional Perspective on Coal in the Late Austro-Hungarian Empire*. In: J. DAHEUR – I. LUČIĆ (Eds.), *Habsburg Natures: Imperial Governance and Environment in Central Europe, 1850–1918*, Berghahn Books 2025, p. 274.

⁷ Simone GINGRICH, *Foreign trade and early industrialisation in the Habsburg Monarchy and the United Kingdom – Two extremes in comparison*, *Ecological Economics* 70, 2011, p. 1281.

⁸ By a ton, the authors mean 1,000 kilograms.

⁹ Cf. PLYER, 274; GINGRICH, 1284.

coal requirements from domestic sources, having to import the rest: 20 percent of its coal from the Ostrava basin and 57 percent from the Upper Silesian basin.¹⁰ The former Ostrava basin contained the richest hard coal deposits in the Monarchy.¹¹ The Bohemian Lands accounted for 90 percent of all Habsburg coal production and heavy industry.¹²

It logically ensues that the Monarchy was energy-dependent even before the outbreak of the war. The extent of its energy-insecurity can be well demonstrated by the fact that during the early 1900s, ‘even the railways of the Bohemian crownlands ran primarily on German coal.’¹³ While Bohemia had some deposits of hard coal, such as Kladno, Pilsen or Ostrava-Karviná, it imported large amounts of German hard coal and also of coke, while exporting large amounts of lignite to Germany.¹⁴ As far as the Monarchy’s coal-dependency is concerned, there were striking differences between the individual parts of the Monarchy: its Austrian part depended on coal to a similar extent as the Western powers did.¹⁵

Generally speaking, war requires an extraordinary mobilisation of all resources, including energy, and it usually results in major disruptions to energy supplies.¹⁶ Throughout 1917, material and energy scarcity fully impacted the Habsburg Monarchy.¹⁷ It also affected the Czech Lands, the industrial heart of the Monarchy, and its urban centres. Prague, then third largest urban centre of the Monarchy,¹⁸ was no exception, and as the war progressed, the city could not satisfy its energy needs anymore. The crisis peaked during the severe winters of 1916–17 and 1917–1918, when Prague, along with other cities within the realm of the Czech Lands,

¹⁰ Cf. PLYER, 274; Jiří MATĚJČEK, *Vývoj uhelného průmyslu v českých zemích po průmyslové revoluci (do roku 1914)*, Prague 1984, 206; Jiří MATĚJČEK, *Ostravsko-karvinský revír v konkurenčním boji s hornoslezským uhelným revírem v letech 1880–1913*, Slezský sborník 67, 1969, no. 4, pp. 456–66.

¹¹ John ROBERTSON, *Calamitous Methods of Compulsion: Labor, War, and Revolution in a Habsburg Industrial District, 1906–1919* (PhD thesis, Chapel Hill 2014), 8.

¹² Aliaksandr PIAHANAU and Per HÖGSELIUS, *Energy Shortages During the Short Coal Age in Europe (1860–1960). An Introduction*, Journal of Energy History, 14, 2025, no. 1, pp.4–28, <https://stm.cairn.info/journal-journal-of-energy-history-2025-1-page-4?lang=en>.

¹³ PLYER, 277.

¹⁴ PLYER, 277.

¹⁵ Marc LANDRY, *Coal Crisis, Hydroelectrification, and Environmental Change in the First Austrian Republic, 1918–1934*, Journal of Energy History/ Revue d’histoire de l’énergie 14, 2025, no. 1, 4.

¹⁶ Vaclav SMIL, *War and Energy*. In: Encyclopedia of Energy, vol. 6, Elsevier 2004, <https://vaclavsmil.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/smil-article-2004-war-and-energy.pdf>

¹⁷ Tamas VONYO, *Demise and Disintegration: The Economic Consequences of the Great War in Central Europe*, in: Stephen BROADBERRY and Mark HARISSON, *The Economics of the Great War, A Centennial Perspective*, London 2018, p. 97.

¹⁸ In 1914, Prague agglomeration consisted of 22 communes and encompassed overall 616,000 inhabitants living in 103,000 apartments. Cf. *Věstník obecní královského hlavního města Prahy*, 9 March 1917, p. 62. On the eve of the First World War, only about 20 percent of Prague’s households were electrified, with electrification especially scarce among the lower-income majority and in suburban areas, where kerosene lighting continued to prevail. Archiv hlavního města Prahy (hereafter AHMP), f. Magistrát hl. města Prahy I (Municipality of Prague, hereafter MHMP I), inv. no. 31–34, Protokoly o schůzích aprovizčních úřadů (Report by the Supply Agencies), sign. 2833 – A.Ú., March 20, 1917, 4.

suffered acute shortages of coal. In some cases, even the operation of enterprises indispensable to the war industry was seriously curtailed.¹⁹ Even the cities located within the proximity of the coal mining areas suffered from the crisis: during the winter of 1917–1918, Škoda Works, the largest ammunition factory of the Monarchy, located in Pilsen, had to limit their operations due to recurring shortages of coal.²⁰ In Prague, a city six times larger than Pilsen, residents experienced the most severe crisis during the first three months of 1917: the city obtaining roughly 300 wagons (tons) of coal instead of 1,500 wagons needed daily. The available data suggest that the coal requirements of the entire Prague agglomeration (including the suburbs, i. e., 22 communes with 100,000 households) during early 1917 corresponded to a daily supply of 320 wagons of coal just for the households (roughly 10 kilograms per family per day), while additional wagons of coal were required for basic municipal infrastructure (such as gasworks, waterworks, energy plants, municipal transportation), hospitals, orphanages, schools, kindergartens and other public institutions.²¹ Consequently, in mid-February 1917, *Venkov* informed that between 1–12 February, Prague obtained only one third of the required coal. In contrast to Prague, it was reported that both Budapest (Pest) and Vienna were experiencing less hardship.²² By early February 1917, the Prague coal calamity was reported to be peaking: *‘All activity has come to a standstill. Schools and institutions are closing, the electric railway is not running, theatres and cinemas are not showing films, restaurants and cafés are limiting their business, the streets are haunted by darkness at night, and the population is searching for coal everywhere in vain.’*²³ By the same time, restrictions and energy-saving measures had been proliferating.

¹⁹ The two largest enterprises in Pilsen were the Škoda Works, whose monthly needs in 1915 equalled 168 wagons of coke (1,680 tonnes), and the Burger’s Brewery, whose monthly needs accounted for 25 wagons of coke (250 tonnes). Státní oblastní archiv Plzeň, Klášter u Nepomuku (hereafter SOAPKL), f. Municipal Gasworks (Městská plynárna), cart. 1, Dozorčí komise, Zápisy ze schůzi dozorčí komise 1914–1919, inv. no. 15, book no. 3, 11 Oct. 1915.

²⁰ Between 15 December 1917 and 2 February 1918, Škoda Works witnessed a complete shutdown due to the coal shortage. Minutes of the Board of Directors of Škoda Works, along with the Smelting records indicate recurrent outages and interruptions of operations, notably later in 1918. Cf. SOAPKL, Škodovy závody akciová společnost, Plzeň – Generální Ředitelství Praha, kart. 4, inv. č. 27; SOAPKL, Škodovy závody akciová společnost, Plzeň, závod Plzeň, Knihy taveb (not yet inventoried); AMP, Minutes of the City Council (hereafter Minutes), sign. 2d6, 14 Dec. 1917; AMP, Minutes, sign. 2d7, 8 Jan. 1918, f. 13.

²¹ Sometimes, supplies were as little as 29–74 wagons of coal daily for the entire Prague including hospitals. Cf. “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, Annex 2, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “Zásobování,” *Věstník obecní královského hlavního města Prahy*, 9 March 1917, p. 62.

²² “Praha, Pešť, Vídeň,” *Venkov*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 1; “Které uhlí musí být pro Prahu zachováno,” *Právo lidu*, 13 Feb. 1917, p. 5.

²³ “Praha, Pešť, Vídeň,” *Venkov*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 1.

This article does not primarily focus on material manifestations of coal scarcity or structural factors underlying the coal crisis, such as disintegration of the railway system.²⁴ Instead, it examines selected Czech-written newspapers and the discursive dimension of the coal crisis. More precisely, it seeks to answer three main research questions: 1. How the scarcity and the energy (coal) crisis was presented and justified in the public debate and how it was suggested to be remembered by the daily press. 2. What were the prevailing frames linked to the coal scarcity? 3. Were these frames consistent or did they change or develop in the period under review?

As far as the period press is concerned, during wartime, the newspapers were strictly censored.²⁵ The formal censorship was organized and implemented by several organs (including the *Kriegsüberwachungsamt*, or later *Ministerialkommission im Kriegsministerium* who issued directives while other bodies implemented them in practice), yet no systemic rules existed, and the practice differed across the Monarchy.²⁶ However, the press still remained the main means of communication with the public and played an important role in shaping public perception and influencing the direction of social discourse.²⁷ The press not only informed the public about the shortages and related outages, but it also shaped the societal perceptions by diffusing coal-scarcity related frames aiming to manage public behaviour. The media framing therefore served the Habsburg Monarchy as ‘a subtle and sophisticated information control strategy’ while playing ‘a critical role in steering public opinion and cultivating an image of competent government during a tremendous crisis’.²⁸ It would therefore be noteworthy to explore this domain of media framing.

This contribution firstly introduces the theoretical underpinnings and methodological choices, including the description of data collection and the data corpus, which is followed by a mixed-methods analysis. From quantitative content analysis, which helped to identify the most prevalent coal-crisis-related collocation, it will focus on qualitative content analysis, that will present the prominent topics related to the most prevalent coal-crisis-related collocation and their pertaining framing. Eventually, it discusses and concludes the main findings.

²⁴ SCHULTZE, 93; R. J. WEGS, Transportation: The Achilles Heel of the Habsburg War Effort, in R. A. KANN – B. KIRÁLY – P. S. FICHTNER (Eds.), *The Habsburg Empire in World War I*, New York 1977, pp. 121–34.

²⁵ See Étienne BOISSERIE, *Les Tchèques dans l’Autriche-Hongrie en guerre*, Paris 2018.

²⁶ See John D. HALLIDAY, *Censorship in Berlin and Vienna during the First World War: A Comparative View*, *The Modern Language Review* 83, No. 3 (1988), pp. 616–617 and 620.

²⁷ Alena KLUKNAVSKÁ, *Game of Frames: A Content Analysis of Politicians Framing of Public Service Media on Facebook and Instagram in the Czech Republic*, *Journal of Contemporary European Studies* 33, 2025, no. 2, p. 672.

²⁸ Xia SHOUZHI – Huang HUANG – Dong ZHANG, *Framing as an Information Control Strategy in Times of Crisis*, *Journal of East Asian Studies* 22, 2022, no. 2, pp. 255–79. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jea.2022.5>.

Theoretical background and methodological approach, the dataset

This paper builds on a premise that ‘human beings are storytelling animals,’ and ‘if stories are important for us as individuals, then it also probably follows that stories must play an important role for groups and the collective action in which these groups engage.’²⁹ Within the critical discourse studies, it is particularly the framing approach³⁰ that underscores the power of a communicating text: ‘to frame is to select some aspects of a perceived reality and make them more salient in a communicating text, in such a way as to promote a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation, and/or treatment recommendation for the item described’.³¹ The frames structure perception, and guide the receiver’s thinking and understanding of complex issues by foregrounding certain elements and aspects of information, thus elevating them in salience and ‘making them more noticeable, meaningful or memorable,’ while at the same time marginalizing and omitting the others.³² While this approach may help to uncover how issues, events or topics are presented and foregrounded or obscured, thus shaping the perception of the audience, the use of content analysis may help to demonstrate how these frames are employed in relation to specific topics – such as coal scarcity.³³

Therefore, this text seeks to examine the content of frames and their use in various Czech-written media during the First World War to explore how energy scarcity and related energy-saving appeals were communicated to the broad public. Methodologically, this article uses a mixed-methods analysis: it proceeds from quantitative content analysis to identify the saliency, frequency and distribution of predefined keywords within the entire corpus in the first part, to the qualitative content analysis to explore the dominant topics and frames related to the notion coal calamity and the context in which they are presented in the second part.

The qualitative content analysis was operationalised inductively, using a data-driven approach, where individual codes and categories were identified while reading the texts.³⁴ The

²⁹ H. HEINELT – Steffek, J., *Narratives in a Nutshell: Capturing the Communicative Effects of Topoi in Political Research*, *Critical Policy Studies*, 2025, 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19460171.2025.2493087>.

³⁰ R. N. ENTMAN, *Framing: Toward Clarification of a Fractured Paradigm*, *Journal of Communication* 43, 1993, no. 4, p. 52, <https://fbaum.unc.edu/teaching/articles/J-Communication-1993-Entman.pdf>; KLUKNAVSKÁ, pp. 672–686; Robert D. BENFORD – David A. SNOW, *Framing Processes and Social Movements: An Overview and Assessment*, *Annual Review of Sociology* 26, 2000, pp. 611–629, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.soc.26.1.611>.

³¹ ENTMAN, p. 53.

³² ENTMAN, p. 53.

³³ J. MATTHES, *What’s in a Frame? A Content Analysis of Media Framing Studies in the World’s Leading Communication Journals, 1990–2005*, *Journalism and Mass Communication Quarterly* 86, 2009, no. 2, p. 349; J. MATTHES – Matthias KOHRING, *The Content Analysis of Media Frames: Toward improving Reliability and Validity*, *Journal of Communication* 58, 2008, no. 2, pp. 258–279, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2008.00384.x>.

³⁴ Margrit SCHREIER, *Qualitative Content Analysis in Practice*, Sage 2012, p. 84.

coding schema was based on systemic process of data reduction and abstraction. First, open coding was applied to the subset of texts to capture initial meaning units related to energy scarcity. These codes were then compared and grouped into broader sub-categories. In the final stage, these categories were synthesized into dominant frames by identifying recurring patterns.³⁵

As for the corpus, the contributions analysed herein were extracted from several Czech-written journals: the right-wing *Národní listy*, agrarian *Venkov*, left-wing *Právo lidu*, social-liberal *Lidové Noviny* (printed in Brno), and *Český deník* and social-liberal *Nová doba* (printed in Pilsen). Furthermore, all these journals allow the OCR-searchable digital format, enabling to apply a mixed-methods approach combining quantification with qualitative analysis. The journals were selected to encompass the voices spanning from the political right to the centre and left.³⁶

By conducting a preliminary quantitative overview using frequency counts and keyword-in-context (KWIC) techniques, we were striving to identify recurring lexical patterns and thematic clusters across the selected historical texts. These findings informed the selection of salient discourse features that could be observed in our corpus for deeper qualitative examination.

Revealing the coverage frequency – quantitative part

The predefined keywords used for the quantitative analysis were: *uhelná kalamita* (coal calamity), *uhelná krize/krise* (coal crisis), *uhelná otázka* (coal question) and *uhelná nouze* (coal poverty). The selected media outlets mention these notions as follows: Table 1: *uhlí (coal)* and *uhlí (coal) AND nedostatek (scarcity)*; and Table 2 for specific collocations. The collocation coal calamity (*uhelná kalamita*), clearly employing emotionally-charged language, was the most frequently present notion within the entire dataset (213 mentions in total).

Coal calamity was mentioned for the first time in 1915 (8 mentions in total), similarly few (9) in 1916, and the frequency of the notion peaks in 1917, where it was present in the dataset for 159 times. In 1918, the frequency diminishes to relatively few notions (37) compared to 1917. Table 2 further demonstrates that collocations such as coal crisis (*uhelná krize/krise*), coal question (*uhelná otázka*) and coal poverty (*uhelná nouze*) were relatively sporadically present within the entire dataset.

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ P. BEDNAŘÍK – J. JIRÁK – B. KÖPPOVÁ, *Dějiny českých médií: od počátku po současnost* [History of Czech Media: From the Beginning to the Present Day], Prague 2011.

<Table 1>

Notion	Uhlí (Coal)	Uhlí + nedostatek (coal AND scarcity)
1914	2127	402
1915	2605	714
1916	3370	908
1917	5888	2059
1918	2528	778

Source: author, based on the dataset

<Table 2>

NOTION	Uhelná kalamita (Coal calamity)	Uhelná krise (Coal crisis)	Uhelná otázka (Coal question)	Uhelná nouze (Coal poverty)
1914	0	0	1	0
1915	8	7	5	0
1916	9	18	7	0
1917	159	66	59	26
1918	37	23	14	12
Total:	213	114	86	38

Source: author, based on the dataset

As Table 1 demonstrates, the media coverage of coal-related news was the highest during 1917, when 5,888 reports included the notion of coal. At the same time, nearly 35 percent of all these reports were related to coal scarcity. Although this quantitative overview shows that the terms coal and coal AND scarcity appear very frequently in the analysed periodicals, they do not in themselves allow us to capture the way in which the problem of energy scarcity was presented, framed, structured and interpreted in terms of the meaning for the public. These general terms often function as neutral descriptive categories and appear in a wide range of texts – from administrative reports to economic statistics to technical information – without necessarily carrying a significant interpretative or appellative charge. In contrast, the collocations, such as coal calamity or coal crisis both represent explicit framing that not only describes the material shortage of coal, but also loads it with value, emotional charge, and places it in the discourse of an exceptional crisis. The qualitative part of the analysis will therefore explore the collocations coal calamity and coal crisis in greater detail.

Before we delve into the qualitative analysis, another quantitative breakdown into the concrete journals and the distribution of the predefined key words across the time span (1914–

1918) might be useful in order to examine the patterns and saliency of coverage in individual journals. Such breakdown further suggests (Table 2–3), that the notion coal calamity was the most frequently present in the dataset in 1917. As Table 3 shows, it was most frequently mentioned by *Právo lidu* (75) and *Národní listy* (51). *Venkov* and *Lidové noviny* mentioned it only 9 and 7 times, respectively. In 1918, *Český deník* even acknowledged the existence of a coal calamity in Vienna.³⁷

<Table 3>

Coal calamity	1914	1915	1916	1917	1918	Total:
Právo lidu	0	1	2	75	16	94
Venkov	0	1	1	12	3	17
Národní listy	0	1	0	51	4	56
Lidové Noviny	0	1	6	7	1	15
Český deník	0	2	0	9	10	21
Nová doba	0	2	0	5	3	10
Total:	0	8	9	159	37	213

Source: author, based on the dataset

Coal calamity was followed in coverage by coal crisis (Table 4), the second most frequent notion within the dataset (114 mentions in total during the time frame 1914–1918). Coal crisis appears in the dataset for the first time in 1915, and a closer look indicates that two of seven mentions in total were related to the situation abroad, more precisely related to enemy, i. e., Moscow.³⁸ In 1916, *Lidové noviny* brought up the notion seven times, mostly referring to the situation abroad, outside the Central Powers.³⁹ Only in March 1917 did they acknowledge certain troubles with coal supply within the Habsburg Monarchy, finally admitting to the coal crisis in Prague in December 1917.⁴⁰ Right-wing *Právo lidu* referred to the coal crisis twice in 1915 (both references were related to the situation in Moscow). In 1916, it covered the coal crisis in France three times but once also in relation to the Czech Lands, more precisely, to *Vysoké Mýto*. In 1917, however, all mentions covered the coal crisis within the Czech Lands,

³⁷ “Uhelná kalamita ve Vídni,” *Český deník*, 16 Nov. 1918, p. 2.

³⁸ “Uhelná krise v Moskvě,” *Lidové Noviny*, 29 April 1915, p. 2.

³⁹ “Uhelná krise francouzská,” *Lidové Noviny*, 18 May 1916, p. 1; “Nová krise uhelná – z Londýna,” *Lidové Noviny*, 15 March 1916, p. 2; “Uhelná krise ve Francii,” *Lidové Noviny*, 18 November 1916, p. 2; “Petit Journal sděluje z Amiensu,” *Lidové Noviny*, 13 November 1916, p. 1; “Uhelná krise ve Francii,” *Lidové Noviny*, 16 Nov. 1916, p. 2; “Nedostatek uhlí v Holandsku,” *Lidové noviny*, 28 Nov. 1916, p. 2; “Dopravní krise ve Francii,” *Právo lidu*, 7 Dec. 1916, p. 4; “Nedostatek ve Francii,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 7 Dec. 1916, p. [12].

⁴⁰ “Národní hospodář: Zajištění potřeby uhlí v Uhrách,” *Lidové Noviny*, p. 16 March 1917, p. 2; “Uhelná krise v Praze,” *Lidové Noviny*, 15 Dec. 1917, p. 4.

be it Pilsen,⁴¹ Pardubice,⁴² Prague,⁴³ or other cities within the Bohemian realm.⁴⁴ The coverage of coal crisis in other countries was also relatively high.⁴⁵ As can be seen in Table 4, *Národní listy* referred to the coal crisis twice in 1915, three times in 1916 and finally, 16 times in 1917. *Venkov* referred to the coal crisis once in 1915, once in 1916, and nine times in 1917.

<Table 4>

Coal crisis	1914	1915	1916	1917	1918	Total
Právo lidu	0	2	5	23	12	42
Venkov	0	1	1	9	3	14
Národní listy	0	2	3	16	3	24
Lidové Noviny	0	0	7	7	0	14
Český deník	0	2	1	7	3	13
Nová doba	0	0	1	4	2	7
Total:	0	7	18	66	23	114

Source: author, based on the dataset

It is perhaps not surprising, that while the notions of coal calamity and coal crisis were only sporadically present in the dataset during the first years of World War I (1914, 1915, 1916), they peaked during the years of 1917 and 1918, corresponding to the wartime progress and overall exhaustion of the Habsburg Empire.⁴⁶ The dramatic increase in the coverage of coal calamity and coal crisis in 1917 (cf. Table 3–4) signals not merely a reflection of the deteriorating supply situation but rather a shift in the framing of the problem. Whereas earlier scarcity was presented as a technical or logistical issue, as shall be demonstrated further, the term calamity introduces affective and moral dimensions in the public discourse, thereby smoothing the path for appeals or foregrounding urgency.

⁴¹ “Z českého západu: Nouze o uhlí v Plzni,” *Právo lidu*, 9 Jan. 1917, p. 7; “Uhelná krise na Plzeňsku,” *Právo lidu*, 18 Feb. 1917, p. 3.

⁴² “Uhelná krise v městě Pardubicích a Sezemicích trvá,” *Právo lidu*, 2 Annex to *Právo lidu*, 21 Jan. 1917, p. 6; “Pardubice za války,” *Národní listy*, 11 Dec. 1917, p. 3; “Uhelná kalamita v Pardubicích,” 16 Dec. 1917, p. 4.

⁴³ “Uhelná kalamita: uhelná krise a školy,” *Právo lidu*, 15 Feb. 1917, p. 3.

⁴⁴ “Uhelná krise ve venkovských městech,” *Právo lidu*, 18 Feb. 1917, p. 5.

⁴⁵ “Uhelná krise v Německu,” *Právo lidu*, 16 Feb. 1917, p. 4; “Uhelná kalamita v Drážďanech,” 6 Feb. 1917, p. 4.

⁴⁶ VONYO, p. 97.

Contextualization

Initially, this section will use content analysis to outline the dominant topics related to coal and scarcity and examine the broader context in which collocations such as coal crisis and coal calamity appear within the dataset. As the quantitative analysis has already suggested, in the earlier stages of war, media coverage of coal and its scarcity was relatively high. However, a closer look at the content reveals that most of the reports deny the existence of scarcity or refer to scarcity outside the Bohemian Lands.⁴⁷ Shortly after the outbreak of war, *Venkov* reported: ‘There is no need to worry about a shortage of coal, as there will surely be enough for all purposes. The current shortage should not mislead anyone, as it is due to a major extraordinary restriction on coal transport, which will improve soon. It is therefore a shortage of wagons and not a shortage of coal.’⁴⁸ At the same time, the press reported that Prague’s electricity companies had two months’ worth of reserves and that current operations were covered by daily coal deliveries.⁴⁹ Later in 1915, reports referred to global coal reserves and deposits, offering reassurance that there will be no shortage of coal anytime soon.⁵⁰

In these earlier stages of war, the coal related reports were mostly linked to mining and the overall coal production, or to the reports on the rising prices of coal.⁵¹ Media also often covered the situation abroad,⁵² especially in enemy countries.⁵³ During the first two years, general transportation and supply issues were frequently covered.⁵⁴ In January 1915, the coal crisis in Prague was mentioned by press, while the journals informed that Prague and its suburbs were facing coal scarcity. The journals explicitly framed the crisis as having one culprit stated that “transportation issues were the reasons behind the coal poverty.”⁵⁵ Yet readers were

⁴⁷ “Zásobování uhlím,” *Venkov*, 27 Aug. 1914, p. 7; “Zásoby uhlí pražských elektrických podniků,” *Venkov*, 27 Aug. 1914, p. 4.

⁴⁸ “Zásobování uhlím,” *Venkov*, 27 Aug. 1914, p. 7.

⁴⁹ “Zásoby uhlí pražských elektrických podniků,” *Venkov*, 27 Aug. 1914, p. 4.

⁵⁰ “Umělé uhlí,” *Právo lidu*, 25 Sept. 1915, p. 2.

⁵¹ “Národní hospodář: Rakouská uhelná těžba v lednu 1915,” *Národní listy*, 2 March 1915, p. 4; “Proti neoprávněnému zdražování uhlí,” *Národní listy*, 13 Nov. 1914, p. 3; “Drahota uhlí,” *Národní listy*, 12 Dec. 1914, p. 3; “Opět dražší uhlí,” *Národní listy*, 29 Dec. 1914, p. 3; “Zdražení uhlí,” *Právo lidu*, 3 Jan. 1915, p. 2; “O stavu trhu hnědouhelného,” *Právo lidu*, 7 Jan. 1915, p. 9.

⁵² “Hospodářské nedostatky v Rusku,” *Lidové noviny*, 1 March 1915, p. 1; “Nedostatek uhlí ve Francii,” *Právo lidu*, 8 Dec. 1916, p. 16; “Poruchy ve francouzském průmyslu,” *Nová doba*, 3 Jan. 1917, p. 1; “Uhelná kalamita v Rusku,” *Nová doba*, 4 Sept. 1917, p. 1.

⁵³ “Strašná bída v ruském Polsku,” *Večer*, 7 Jan. 1915, p. 3; “Obchod a průmysl za války. O uhlí,” *Venkov*, 28 Dec. 1916, p. 4; “Beseda: noviny ve válce,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 31 Jan. 1917, p. 1; “Různé zprávy z Itálie,” *Národní listy*, 3 March 1916, p. 2.

⁵⁴ “Stížnosti do trvajícího nedostatku vagonů,” *Národní listy*, 2 March 1915, p. 5; “Uhlí,” *Národní listy*, 1 Dec. 1915, p. 4.

⁵⁵ “K uhelné otázce v Praze,” *Národní listy*, 15 Jan. 1915, p. 4.

reassured that the Monarchy had sufficient resources and that the situation was caused by the lack of transportation wagons.⁵⁶ Similarly, in early March 1915, *Národní listy* reported on the situation in Smíchov, one of Prague suburbs, and concluded that due to insufficient number of transportations wagons the coal supply for Prague waterworks and power plants was jeopardized.⁵⁷ The local City Council had to intervene in Vienna to secure priority wagons for coal supply. It also contracted further supplies with private companies.⁵⁸

Based on media reports in 1915, coal still seemed available, notwithstanding the increased price rates.⁵⁹ The coal crisis was publicly presented rather as a crisis of affordability than availability. Therefore, the rising prices of coal were also often thematized, yet without the link to calamity and without the presence of a crisis-laden language. To exemplify this, in 1915, the media outlets presented purely informative articles on rising prices of coal, without suggesting that rising prices meant scarcity or even interruption in operation of municipal utilities, such as waterworks or gasworks.⁶⁰ Since late 1916, however, as the war progressed, the topic of energy-saving gained prominence,⁶¹ implicitly indicating that coal became much scarcer. By December 1916, the coal crisis had gained prominence in media-presented discourse, and so did the responsibility related to it: for instance, readers were again informed that the coal supply problems were caused by insufficient number of wagons for coal transportation.⁶² However, from 1917 onwards, the discourse on coal calamity prevailed. In contrast to coal crisis, collocations with the term calamity corresponded to increasingly emotive and moralizing framing, in contrast to crisis, which indicated rather a structural issue. Calamity gained prominence especially within the first three months of the year,⁶³ and at the turn of 1917

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵⁷ “Smíchov za války,” *Národní listy*, 6 March 1915, pp. 3–4.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

⁵⁹ “O stavu trhu hnědouhelného,” *Právo lidu*, 7 Jan. 1915, p. 9.

⁶⁰ Cf. Cenzurováno, *Právo lidu*, 1 Dec. 1915, p. 5; “Zásobování,” *Právo lidu*, 10 Dec. 1917, p. 6.

⁶¹ “Šetřte káranskou vodou!” *Národní listy*, 28 Dec. 1916, p. 4; “Praha beze světla,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 7 Dec. 1916, p. [13]; “Také ve Vídni se bude šetřit plynem,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 7 Dec. 1916, p. [13]; “Obchod a průmysl za války. O uhlí,” *Venkov*, 28 Dec. 1916, p. 4.

⁶² “Nedostatek železničních vagonů v uhelných revírech,” *Venkov*, 28 Dec. 1916, p. 4; “A pak je prý nouze o vagony,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 7 Dec. 1916, p. [13], Annex, 7 Dec. 1916, p. [13]; “Zimní prázdniny ve školách?,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 7 Dec. 1916, p. [13], Annex, 7 Dec. 1916, p. [13].

⁶³ “Svícení plynem a uhelná kalamita v Praze,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 31 Jan. 1917, s. p.; “Uhelná kalamita v Praze,” *Lidové noviny*, 8 Feb. 1917, p. 5; “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, 9 Feb. 1917, p. 4; “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, 10 Feb. 1917, p. 1 and pp. 3–4; “Uhelná kalamita a omezené osvětlení,” *Právo lidu*, 10 Feb. 1917, p. 11; “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, 11 Feb. 1917, p. 10; “Uhelná kalamita trvá dále,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 11 Feb. 1917, p. 9; “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, 15 Feb. 1917, p. 3; “Uhelná kalamita, stav nezměněn,” *Právo lidu*, 16 Feb. 1917, p. 13; “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 4; “K uhelné krizi,” *Právo lidu*, 11 March 1917, p. 4; “Z Pojizeří,” *Právo lidu*, 11 March 1917, pp. 5–6; “Doprava uhlí do Prahy po vodě,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 5 May 1917, s. p.; “Co je to rekvisiční uhlí,” *Právo lidu*, 25 May 1917, p. 5; “Uhelná kalamita a obleva,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “Praha, Pešť, Vídeň,” *Venkov*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 1.

and 1918, corresponding to the winter seasons.⁶⁴ While in Prague the topic was more prominent in early 1917, in Pilsen and other cities, such as Pardubice, the coal calamity, at least in the public debate, also persisted later in 1917 and 1918.⁶⁵

From 1916 onwards, the most prominent topics were coal scarcity and insufficient coal supply in general,⁶⁶ shortages,⁶⁷ outages,⁶⁸ omnipresent queues,⁶⁹ and restrictions on energy consumption,⁷⁰ along with official instructions and actions⁷¹ to either prevent or ease the calamity.⁷² Finally, the possible effects of the energy crisis and enforced school closures on future generations were also repeatedly thematized.⁷³ In this context, *Právo lidu*, for example, reiterated the famous declaration by Empress Zita: “Everything for the Well-Being of Children! (Vše pro blaho dětí!)”⁷⁴ and warned that enforced school closures were a profound mistake: “*We believe that every sensible person with a heart in the right place and at least a sense of responsibility for the upbringing of future generations recognizes and feels that closing schools today amidst the chaos of war and leaving children to chance and street influence would be the most outrageous mistake and a heavy blow for the future of human society and the nation.*”⁷⁵ This warning notwithstanding, the coal calamity made the enforced closures inevitable.

Prominent topics linked with the second most frequent key phrase within the dataset, the coal crisis, were very similar. First, the press mentioned the existence of a coal crisis

⁶⁴ “Uhelná kalamita v Praze a školy,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 25 Oct. 1917, s.p.; “Světová kalamita uhelná,” *Český deník*, 16 Sept. 1917, p. 4.

⁶⁵ “Uhelná kalamita,” *Venkov*, 24 Sept. 1918, p. 6; “Školní prázdniny v zimě,” *Venkov*, 24 Sept. 1918, p. 6; “Uhelná kalamita v Plzni,” *Nová doba*, 24 Jan. 1918, p. 3; “Uhelná kalamita v Praze,” *Právo lidu*, 31 Jan. 1917, p. 3; “Uhelná kalamita v Praze,” *Národní listy*, 12 Feb. 1917, p. 2; “Před krutými dobami,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 10 Aug. 1917, s. p.; “Uhelná kalamita v Praze,” 11 Jan. 1918, p. 5; “Kladno nemá uhlí,” *Venkov*, 10 Aug. 1918, p. 5.

⁶⁶ “Dvacet devět vagonů místo sta,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “Tramway pouze do osmi hodin večer,” *Právo lidu*, 27 Jan. 1917, p. 6.

⁶⁷ “Nedostatek uhlí v Praze,” *Lidové noviny*, 13 March 1917, p. 4; “Kam dopravuje se naše uhlí?” *Lidové noviny*, 23 Feb. 1917, p. 5; “Správní rada vodárny král. hlav. města Prahy,” *Národní listy*, 24 Feb. 1917, p. 4.

⁶⁸ “Plynová kalamita v Praze,” *Lidové noviny*, 28 Jan. 1917, p. 5; “Krise elektrických drah pražských,” *Národní listy*, 9 Feb. 1917, p. 1; “Pražská tramway a nouze o uhlí,” *Právo lidu*, 8 Dec. 1916, p. 6; “Kladno 16 hodin bez osvětlení elektrického,” *Lidové noviny*, 14 Jan. 1917, p. 4.

⁶⁹ “Mrzne,” *Právo lidu*, 27 Jan. 1917, p. 5; “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, 10 Feb. 1917, p. 4; “Zimní prázdniny na školách?” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 7 Dec. 1916, p. [13].

⁷⁰ “Z Karlína: Šetřte vodou!” *Národní listy*, 6 Jan. 1917, p. 6; “Zabezpečení funkce káranského vodovodu,” *Národní listy*, 6 Jan. 1917, p. 4; “Divadla a uhelná kalamita,” and “Koncerty zakázány,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “Omezení užívání plynu v Praze,” *Právo lidu*, 27 Jan. 1917, p. 5; “Uhelná kalamita: Jak se bude šetřit topením a svícením v úřadech,” *Právo lidu*, 26 Jan. 1917, p. 5.

⁷¹ “Uhelná kalamita: péče císařova o Pešť,” *Národní listy*, 12 Feb. 1917, p. 3.

⁷² “Možno očekávati zlepšení v zásobování uhlím?” *Právo lidu*, 30 Jan. 1917, p. 13; “Svícení plynem a uhelná kalamita v Praze,” *Právo lidu*, Annex to No. 29, 31 Jan. 1917, s. p.; “Nedostatek uhlí omezuje i přednášky na universitě,” *Národní listy*, 9 Feb. 1917, p. 3; “Zimní prázdniny ve škole,” *Národní listy*, 9 Dec. 1916, p. 4; “Nedostatek uhlí a školy,” *Právo lidu*, 8 Dec. 1916, p. 6; “Nedostatek uhlí omezuje i přednášky na univerzitě,” *Národní listy*, 9 Feb. 1917, p. 3.

⁷³ “Školy ve Vršovcích,” *Právo lidu*, 12 Jan. 1917, p. 5; “Uhlí ze škol bude bráno pro potřebu pekáren a jiných podniků,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 24 Jan. 1917, s. p.; “Delší pololetní prázdniny?” *Právo lidu*, 24 Jan. 1917, p. 4.

⁷⁴ “Uhelná kalamita: uhelná krise a školy,” *Právo lidu*, 15 Feb. 1917, p. 3.

⁷⁵ *Ibid.*

abroad,⁷⁶ while later, in particular during 1917, the existence of coal crisis within the Monarchy was acknowledged.⁷⁷ Similarly to the coal calamity, prominent topics included savings, queues, government actions to mitigate the crisis, and reports related to coal-related delinquencies.⁷⁸ While it might be argued that the peaking numbers of coal scarcity, crisis or calamity textual distribution during 1917 could be stemming from the less strict censorship introduced after the accession of the new Emperor, Charles I, by early 1917 the Habsburg Monarchy was in fact experiencing severe material crises and deep exhaustion: ‘In the winter of 1916–17 Austrian civilians experienced severe coal and food shortages that left them cold, hungry, exhausted, and discouraged.’⁷⁹

Framing the calamity

This section firstly outlines the context and then proceeds to the related framing strategies used to interpret the coal calamity. To identify the key framing strategies linked to the coal calamity, a second, in-depth level of analysis was employed. Such statements aim to persuade or influence the audience, either explicitly or implicitly.⁸⁰ The analysis revealed the following principal frames related to the coal calamity: reassurance,⁸¹ savings,⁸² solidarity,⁸³ scarcity,⁸⁴ suffering,⁸⁵ and otherness.⁸⁶ The frame of reassurance, employed under censorship, initially presented the calamity as the problem of affordability.⁸⁷ During late 1916 and early

⁷⁶ “Uhelná krise ve Francii,” *Národní listy*, 12 Feb. 1917, p. 2; “Uhelná krise v Německu,” *Právo lidu*, 16 Feb. 1917, p. 4; “Italský průmysl bez uhlí,” *Právo lidu*, 13 Feb. 1917, Annex 2, s. p.; “Uhelná kalamita ve Finsku,” *Národní listy*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 2.

⁷⁷ “Uhelná krise: nesnáze s uhlím ve Vídni,” *Národní listy*, 4 Feb. 1917, p. 3; “Uhelná kalamita v Budapešti,” *Právo lidu*, 13 Feb. 1917, p. 5; “Vídeň bez elektrického proudu,” *Právo lidu*, Annex 2, 13 Feb. 1917.

⁷⁸ “Soudní síň,” *Právo lidu*, 29 March 1916, p. 7; “Různé příhody v Plzni,” *Nová doba*, 10 Feb. 1917, p. 3; “Krádeže uhlí,” *Lidové noviny*, 27 Jan. 1916, p. 4; “Následky nedostatku topiva,” *Lidové noviny*, 14 Jan. 1917, p. 4; “Zatčená černoška,” *Právo lidu*, 14 Jan. 1917, p. 6; “Šetření světlem na Smíchově,” *Právo lidu*, 14 Jan. 1917, p. 6.

⁷⁹ John J. Morrow, Jr., *The Great War: An Imperial History*, Routledge 2014, 210.

⁸⁰ Cf. *Heinelt / Steffek*, 2–3; *Zagar*, I. Z.: Topoi in Critical Discourse Analysis. In: *Lodz Papers in Pragmatics* 6 (2010), no. 1, 3–27.

⁸¹ “Uhelná krise: nesnáze s uhlím ve Vídni,” *Národní listy*, 4 Feb. 1917, p. 3.

⁸² “Obmezené úřadování v družstevních podnicích,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “Šetření světlem na Smíchově,” *Právo lidu*, 14 Jan. 1917, p. 6.

⁸³ “Krise elektrických drah pražských,” *Národní listy*, 9 Feb. 1917, p. 1; “Uhelná kalamita v Praze,” *Národní listy*, 9 Feb. 1917, p. 3; “Uhlí ze škol bude bráno pro potřebu pekáren a jiných podniků,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 24 Jan. 1917, s. p.; “Ohřívárny pro chudé školní dívky a jich stravování ve školách,” *Národní listy*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 3.

⁸⁴ “Mrzne,” *Právo lidu*, 27 Jan. 1917, p. 5; “Nouze o uhlí v Praze,” *Lidové noviny*, 19 Jan. 1917, p. 4; “Světová válka a uhlí,” *Právo lidu*, 18 Feb. 1917, p. 1; “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 17 Feb. 1917, p. [13].

⁸⁵ “Mrzne,” *Právo lidu*, 27 Jan. 1917, p. 5; “Uhelná kalamita. Proč nejedí elektrické dráhy?” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, p. [13]; “Uhelná kalamita,” *Nová doba*, 14 Feb. 1917, p. 1; “Doprava na městských elektrických drahách v Praze zastavena,” *Národní listy*, 9 Feb. 1917, p. 3.

⁸⁶ “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, pp. [4–5]; “Jak se dělá nálada místo – uhlí pro Prahu,” *Národní listy*, 15 Aug. 1917, pp. 2–3.

⁸⁷ “Různé zprávy: Zvýšení cen uhlí?,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 8 Dec. 1915, p. [15]; “Nesnáze s uhlím,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 26 Nov. 1915, p. [14]; “Nové zdražení uhlí jest na obzoru,” *Lidové noviny*, 30 Nov. 1916, p. 3; “Zásobování

1917, the media coverage depicted the calamity as a challenge to state authorities, emphasizing patience while awaiting the introduction of necessary measures.⁸⁸

The earliest references to the coal calamity, the most frequently mentioned notion within the dataset, appear in December 1915: *Národní listy* on 1 December 1915,⁸⁹ and *Právo lidu* of the same date, however, in the latter journal, the report was grossly censored.⁹⁰ During late 1915, a frame of reassurance was evident, with the press asserting that sufficient coal supplies existed as the combustible was no longer being exported to foreign countries. Coal mines owners were blamed for the coal calamity and threatened with requisitioning.⁹¹ Therefore, responsibility was deflected from the state and the authorities and redirected towards private industries and coal mine owners, who were publicly accused of profiteering. Despite these assurances, and the use of crisis terminology, the coal calamity in public discourse remained a marginal and contained topic throughout 1915–1916.

However, as the war progressed, this framing shifted markedly, notably from 1916 onwards. It evolved from the initial crisis of affordability (1915) into a systemic crisis of availability, intensified during the winter of 1916–1917⁹² and persisting through 1917–1918.⁹³ By early 1917, the calamity had become a prominent and recurring issue within the public debate.⁹⁴ The press reports focused on restrictions of public life, limitations of public services,⁹⁵ government interventions,⁹⁶ enforced closures of entertainment venues,⁹⁷ and overall disruption

uhlím,” *Lidové noviny*, 30 Nov. 1916, p. 3; “Uhlí blízko šachet,” *Lidové noviny*, 18 Nov. 1916, p. 2; “Těžba a doprava uhlí v Čechách v roce 1915,” *Právo lidu*, 16 Aug. 1916, p. 9; “Národní hospodář,” *Právo lidu*, 28 Nov. 1916, p. 9; “Proti zásobování a drahotě,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 6 Jan. 1917, p. 10.

⁸⁸ “Letní den v Rakousku,” *Právo lidu*, 16 April 1916, p. 5; “Letní čas a hornictvo,” *Právo lidu*, 18 May 1916, p. 4; “Pražská elektrika jen do 8 hodin. Omezení dodávky plynu,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 28 Jan. 1917, p. [11]; “Nedostatek uhlí ohrožuje divadla?,” *Právo lidu*, 28 Jan. 1917, p. 5; “Uhelná kalamita: Uhlenky v Praze,” *Právo lidu*, 10 Feb. 1917, p. 4; “Pro nedostatek uhlí zavřené školy,” *Právo lidu*, 10 Feb. 1917, p. 4; “Omezení úředních hodin na hlavní poště,” *Nová doba*, 11 Oct. 1917, p. 3; “Uhelná kalamita,” *Nová doba*, 14 Feb. 1917, p. 1.

⁸⁹ “Uhlí,” *Národní listy*, 1 Dec. 1915, p. [4].

⁹⁰ “Říšský poslanec soudr. Němec intervenoval,” *Právo lidu*, 1 Dec. 1915, p. 5.

⁹¹ *Ibid.*

⁹² “Drahé uhlí ze Sosnovic,” *Národní listy*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 3.

⁹³ “Uhelná kalamita v Roudnici nad Labem,” *Právo lidu*, 10 Dec. 1916, p. 2; “Uhelná kalamita v Pardubicích,” *Právo lidu*, 26 Nov. 1916, p. 4.

⁹⁴ “Uhelná kalamita: Pamětní spis obce pražské o odstranění nedostatku uhlí v Praze,” *Národní listy*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 3; “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, Annex 2, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “Uhelná kalamita v Drážďanech,” 6 Feb. 1917, p. 4; “Videň bez elektrického proudu,” *Právo lidu*, Annex 2, 13 Feb. 1917; “Svícení plynem a uhelná kalamita v Praze,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 31 Jan. 1917, s. p.; “Uhelná kalamita v Praze,” *Národní listy*, 12 Feb. 1917, p. 2; “Dopravní obtíže,” *Právo lidu*, Annex 2, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “O účinku ponorkové války na zaopatřování Anglie,” *Právo lidu*, Annex 2, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.

⁹⁵ “Uhelná kalamita: Proč nejedí elektrické dráhy?” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “Dočasně zrušené vlaky,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “Trampoty lékařů,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “Zkušenosti s omezenou vozbou na tramwayích,” *Právo lidu*, 16 Feb. 1917, p. 4.

⁹⁶ “Zásobování a výživa lidu: ministr Höfer o vyživovacích otázkách,” *Národní listy*, 5 Feb. 1917, p. 3.

⁹⁷ “Biografie v celých Čechách od zítřka uzavřeny,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, s. p.; “Uhelná kalamita a divadla,” *Právo lidu*, 16 Feb. 1917, p. 4.

of daily life, particularly in Bohemia but occasionally also abroad.⁹⁸ The earlier reassurance framing was gradually replaced by openly critical discourse, and disciplinarian language, reflecting both worsening conditions on ground and a loosening censorship under the new emperor, Charles I.

Over time, this reassurance was gradually replaced by the frame of scarcity (both explicitly and implicitly),⁹⁹ and the frame of suffering, which was particularly pervasive. Reports highlighted the fact that working-class households were the most vulnerable.¹⁰⁰ For example, *Právo lidu* described how Prague residents endured severe hardships, with workers braving harsh frosts and tram service disruptions amid the ongoing coal shortage: “The Prague Municipality allowed workers to walk hours to work and completely halted tram services amidst the harshest frosts...” at times, “when the worst coal crisis ever experienced by Prague occurred, and the residents were facing the shortages of coal, wood, and lack of organization and wagons.”¹⁰¹ Prague coal calamity was compared to that in Vienna and Prague city council was criticized for the steps taken in mitigating the energy crisis. However, in early 1917, reports suggested Prague faced a more severe situation, even risking the cessation of drinking water supplies from Káraný by mid-February.¹⁰² Prague coal calamity was reported to be more serious even in comparison to other Bohemian cities, such as Pilsen.¹⁰³

With the progress of war, the coal crisis peaked. By early 1917, the scarcity and overall wartime exhaustion intensified due to harsh weather. Consequently, the media adopted an increasingly authoritarian tone. *Právo lidu* urged the public to conserve water to avoid the shutdown of waterworks, explicitly linking this to coal savings. The tone became disciplinary, with warnings that households could be punished for individual waste, and citizens were encouraged to monitor their neighbours’ behaviour. Similar language and tone were used in public appeals for gas and electricity conservation, with the threat of a complete shutdown of Prague’s gasworks framed as a collective calamity.¹⁰⁴

Within this discourse, media outlets such as *Právo lidu* and *Lidové Noviny* began framing the situation with crisis-laden language, depicting the coal calamity as socially volatile,

⁹⁸ “Uzavření škol, zábavních místností atd. v různých městech,” *Národní listy*, 4 Feb. 1917, p. 4; “Zavření mnichovských škol,” *Národní listy*, 4 Feb. 1917, p. 4.

⁹⁹ “Drahé uhlí ze Sosnovic,” *Národní listy*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 3; “Praze je dodávána pouze třetina slíbeného uhlí,” *Právo lidu*, 16 Feb. 1917, p. 4; “Žádné uhlí pro soukromé odběratele,” *Právo lidu*, 8 Dec. 1916, p. 6.

¹⁰⁰ “Uhelná kalamita,” *Nová doba*, 14 Feb. 1917, p. 1.

¹⁰¹ “Uhelná kalamita. Proč nejezdí elektrické dráhy?” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, p. [13].

¹⁰² “Pitná voda z Káraného,” *Venkov*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 7.

¹⁰³ “Uhelná kalamita,” *Nová doba*, 14 Feb. 1917, p. 1; “Zásobování Plzně uhlím,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Jan. 1917, p. [13].

¹⁰⁴ “Šetřete káranskou vodou,” *Právo lidu*, 4 Jan. 1917, p. 4; “Šetřte vodou,” *Právo lidu*, 2.1.1917, p. 5; “Plynová kalamita v Praze,” *Lidové noviny*, 28 Jan. 1917, p. 5; “Plynová kalamita,” *Lidové noviny*, 1 Feb. 1917, p. 4.

citing stampedes, cold-related deaths, suffering, and impact on the poor.¹⁰⁵ The press appealed: “It is precisely the poorest and middle classes who are without coal. We must keep repeating that we consider it a matter of intelligence and responsibility on the part of the authorities to take immediate action to end the immense suffering of the poor people of Prague”.¹⁰⁶

The frame of otherness was particularly evident in the Prague-based press, which expressed frustration that Prague, despite its proximity to Kladno coal mines, lacked sufficient coal supplies, receiving only 40% of the required coal.¹⁰⁷ Similarly, it was noted that other cities located within the proximity of coal mines, lacked coal supplies, while coal was still being delivered abroad.¹⁰⁸ The press used a responsibility frame by initially blaming the local Czech municipalities for inadequate coal policies and mitigation measures.¹⁰⁹ For example, *Právo lidu* reported that “1,400 wagons of coal were delivered to Vienna in a single day ... That is why Vienna did not experience the same situation as Prague, where factories were threatened with closure and where all the poor had to do without coal in the worst frosts that Prague had ever seen. At the same time, 29–74 wagons of coal were delivered to Prague every day, part of which had to be released to hospitals that had no coal supplies. Therefore, it can be predicted that now that Vienna's coal consumption has been satisfied, Prague will also be supplied, and that later other Czech cities will also be supplied with coal”.¹¹⁰ *Právo lidu* further noted that Prague was not the only city where insufficient coal supplies caused large outages, especially in the gasworks, leaving cities plunged in darkness.¹¹¹

As the coal calamity persisted, however, the media grew resentful of Vienna’s alleged preferential treatment. Reports highlighted that daily coal deliveries, “30–44 wagons of hard coal” from Kladno destined to Prague and other cities were increasingly frequently diverted to Vienna.¹¹² Venkov noted the paradox that even within a country with rich coal reserves, Prague suffered the most: “*In Vienna, too, conditions are not as difficult as they are here ... Minister Trnka took steps to have coal supplies brought to Vienna, which greatly helped the entire population there. ... So how is it that our capital city suffers the most from the coal shortage of*

¹⁰⁵ “Boj o uhlí,” *Právo lidu*, 2 Jan. 1917, p. 6; “Mrzne,” *Právo lidu*, 27 Jan. 1917, p. 5; “Mráz trvá dale,” *Právo lidu*, 6 Feb. 1917, p. 7.

¹⁰⁶ Emphasis in the original. “Mráz trvá dale,” *Právo lidu*, 6 Feb. 1917, p. 7.

¹⁰⁷ “Které uhlí musí být pro Prahu zachováno,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, p. [5].

¹⁰⁸ “Uhelná zvláštnost,” *Lidové noviny*, 20 Feb. 1917, p. 4.

¹⁰⁹ “Uhelná kalamita. Proč nejedí elektrické dráhy?” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, p. [13].

¹¹⁰ “Uhelná kalamita,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, p. [4].

¹¹¹ “Pražská elektrika jen do 8 hodin. Omezení dodávky plynu,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 28 Jan. 1917, p. [11].

¹¹² “Které uhlí musí být pro Prahu zachováno,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 13 Feb. 1917, p. [5].

all the major cities in Austria?”¹¹³ This comparison’s aim was to delegitimize the central government’s organisational capacity.

The frame of otherness gradually evolved to the critique of economic irrationality. Therefore, Venkov blamed the state’s systemic planning and overall organization of coal supply including the allocation priorities.¹¹⁴ Despite increased production, coal exports to Germany persisted, often using German wagons, further aggravating shortages.¹¹⁵ The press, such as *Lidové noviny*, also criticized the absence of timely or practical strategies, resulting in absurdities such as coal from Kladno being transported to Hungary while Prague faced shortages, and was forced to order expensive coal from further located Silesia. This critique then gradually evolved into a discourse of structural grievance, emphasizing Vienna’s preferential treatment: “1,500 wagons of coal from Kladno daily for Vienna, while Prague schools remain closed.”¹¹⁶ *Právo lidu* further informed that while Czech-mined coal was delivered to Vienna, Prague municipal enterprises had to order coal from Sosnowitz at double price.¹¹⁷ By framing the calamity through the above “otherness”, the Czech-written press effectively transformed a material crisis into a powerful narrative of national and regional marginalisation within the crumbling Monarchy.

The press also contrasted Prague’s strict restrictions—including a one 60-watt-bulb rule per household rule—with conditions in Vienna and Berlin, depicted as more lenient. It argued that similar measures were deemed impossible due to scale.¹¹⁸ The discourse evolved into a broader structural critique, emphasizing the shortages of wagons, unequal distribution of resources and the neglect of Prague’s needs in favour of Vienna.¹¹⁹

Conclusion and discussion

This contribution has demonstrated that the coal crisis in Prague (1914–1918) was not merely a logistical failure of the wartime economy but a transformative discursive event that undermined the legitimacy of the Monarchy in the Czech-written public debate. The discourse surrounding the coal calamity during 1915–1918 exemplified clear evolution of media frames of coal scarcity and its public perception in the wartime. The mixed-methods analysis revealed

¹¹³ “Praha, Pešť, Vídeň,” *Venkov*, 17 Feb. 1917, p. 1.

¹¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁵ “Národní hospodář. Naše hospodářská balance za r. 1916,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 9.1.1917, p. [8].

¹¹⁶ “Nouze o uhlí v Praze,” *Národní listy*, 14 Jan. 1917, p. 4; “Z českého severu,” *Právo lidu*, 2 Annex, 14 Jan. 1917, p. [6].

¹¹⁷ “Uhelná kalamita: cesta za uhlím,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 17 Feb. 1917, p. [13].

¹¹⁸ “Pražská elektrika jen do 8 hodin. Omezení dodávky plynu,” *Právo lidu*, Annex, 28 Jan. 1917, p. [11].

¹¹⁹ “Nouze o uhlí v Praze,” *Lidové noviny*, 14 Jan. 1917, p. 4.

shifts from an initial reassurance frame (1915) to a discourse of structural grievance (1917–1918).

In the earlier phases of the war, coal scarcity was framed through reassurance, allowing the authorities and media to mitigate panic by emphasizing coal availability and advocating patience. However, when shortages deepened with the war progress, and when their socioeconomic repercussions became increasingly apparent, the dominant narrative transitioned towards themes of scarcity, suffering, and social vulnerability.

The explosion of coal calamity in the press coverage during early 1917 coincided with a shift towards emotive and moralizing language. The media focused on hardships endured by populations in need and the structural deficiencies of resource allocation. The frame of otherness was used with increasing frequency, framing scarcity because of unequal distribution of coal, and of the alleged preferential treatment accorded to Vienna at the expense of Prague and other Czech cities, thus underscoring systemic and political tensions. The media shift in tone from reassurance to structural grievance reflects not only the escalation of the crisis but also its profound implications for social solidarity and state capacity. The Czech-written press successfully transformed material suffering into a narrative of regional and national marginalisation. By contrasting Prague freezing households with the situation in Vienna, the media effectively redefined the energy crisis as a symptom of an unjust and failing imperial system.

The identified media frames were discursively constructed to manage public behaviour and perception during a time of energy insecurity. By mobilizing emotional and moral appeals rather than offering concrete solutions, they exposed the limitations of the state's capacity to manage the crisis materially, relying instead on rhetorical strategies to maintain control and compliance. The relative absence of practical energy-saving pieces of advice in daily press, despite widespread calls for savings and sacrifice, highlights a limited level of national preparedness and a tendency to favour symbolic over structural solutions. Furthermore, the proposed analysis reveals not only the strategic significance of coal but also the fragility of the coal-dependent system, where any disruption could cause a cascading effect threatening national stability. Additionally, it emphasizes that reliance on coal made urban communities susceptible to both material shortages and manipulative discursive practices.

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